

Cyclohepta[*b*]thiophene derivatives. Part-IV. Dehydrogenation of cyclohepta[*b*]thiophene and cyclohepta[*c*]thiophene derivatives

Sikha Lahiri and P. K. Sen*

Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta-700 073, India

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Cyclohepta[*b*]thiophenes **3** and cyclohepta[*c*]thiophene **4** on dehydrogenation with selenium give a complex mixture of dehydrogenated products. The formation of the identified products is explained through the initial homolytic cleavage at more than one particular bond in the cycloheptane moiety of **3** and **4**. In all these cases ring contraction of the seven-membered ring of the thiophenes **3** and **4** is observed.

Sen *et al*¹ reported synthesis and dehydrogenation of several benzsuberans (**1**). For example, when **1a** is dehydrogenated catalytically with 10% Pd-C in a sealed tube at 380–400° gives 2-methylnaphthalene as the main product.

1

- a $R^1 = R^2 = \text{CH}_3$
- b $R^1 R^2 = -(\text{CH}_2)_4$
- c $R^1 R^2 = -(\text{CH}_2)_5$

The aromatisation process which involves contraction of the seven-membered carbocyclic ring and loss of two carbon atoms has been explained to proceed by homolysis of the C₅-C₆ (or the equivalent C₈-C₉) bond to a biradical followed by its cyclisation and subsequent dehydrogenation with concomitant elimination of the angular methyl group and one of the *gem*-methyl groups from the quaternary carbon atom.

Sen and Lahiri² reported the formation of a complex mixture of several products on selenium dehydrogenation

2

- a $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = \text{H}$
- b $R^1 = R^3 = \text{H}, R^2 = \text{CH}_3$
- c $R^1 = R^2 = \text{CH}_3, R^3 = \text{H}$
- d $R^1 = R^2 = \text{H}, R^3 = \text{CH}_3$

of each of the cyclohepta[*b*]thiophenes (**2**). For example, from **2c**, 2,5-dimethylbenzo[*b*]thiophene was identified as one of the dehydrogenation products but no other products could be identified. Non-equivalent nature of the allylic carbons (C₄ and C₈) in cyclohepta[*b*]thiophenes (**2**) entails that the dehydrogenation process may involve homolytic cleavage at more than one particular bond (C₄-C₅ or C₇-C₈) in its cycloheptane moiety and subsequent disproportionation, cyclisation and aromatisation may give rise to several products. The possibility of the cleavage of the bonds other than allylic ones cannot be ruled out.

In order to test the generality or otherwise of the above mechanism, we have studied dehydrogenation of cyclohepta[*b*]thiophenes (**3**) cyclohepta[*c*]thiophene (**4**). Syntheses of **3** and **4** were reported earlier³. The thiophenes (**3**) may be regarded as 6,6-dialkyl substituted cyclohepta[*b*]thiophenes. **3a** when subjected to selenium dehydrogenation at 380–400° for 12 h, yielded a complex mixture

3

4

- a $n = 4$
- b $n = 5$

evidenced by the glc profile of the dehydrogenation product taken in column OV-17. The peaks appearing at 1.54 and 8.21 min could be enhanced by co-injection with authentic synthesised samples of 2,5-dimethylbenzo[*b*]thiophene² (**5**) and 2-methylnaphtho[2,3-*b*]thiophene (**6**) respectively, whereas co-injection of the synthesised hydrocarbon 2-methylnaphtho[1,2-*b*]thiophene⁴ (**7**) enhanced the peak having retention time 10.43 min.

5

6 R = H

11 R = OAc

7

8

9 R = R' = O

10 R = R' = H

The authentic sample (6) was synthesised by the procedure as described for the synthesis of the corresponding 2-unsubstituted thiophene. The keto acid (9) obtained by Friedel-Crafts condensation of 2-methylthiophene with ph-

thalic anhydride was reduced by zinc dust in aqueous ammonia solution containing catalytic amount of copper sulphate and the resultant acid (10) was converted to the acetoxynaphthothiophene (11) by zinc chloride and acetic anhydride. Digestion of the thiophene (11) with zinc dust in alkali completed the synthesis of the requisite reference compound (6).

Scheme 1

by co-glc experiment. Dehydrogenation of cyclohepta[*c*]thiophene (4) under similar condition afforded a complex mixture of products out of which only 2,7-dimethylbenzo[*c*]thiophene (8) could be identified as one of the constituents by co-glc technique.

It is difficult to explain satisfactorily the plausible mode of fragmentation in the above dehydrogenation reactions. Here also, due to non-equivalent nature of the allylic carbons (C_4 and C_8), initial homolytic cleavage will occur between C_4 - C_5 (Path-*a*) or between C_7 - C_8 (Path-*b*) (Schemes 1 and 2). The possibility of cleavage other than allylic ones cannot be ruled out. As a result, a complex mixture of dehydrogenation products is formed. A plausible explanation of the formation of the identified dehydrogenated products 5, 6 and 7 from 3a, 5 and 7 from 3b and 8 from 4 is depicted in Schemes 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Scheme 3

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) and pmr spectra (CDCl_3 , unless otherwise stated) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer (δ , ppm downfield from TMS internal reference). Glc was carried out on a Shimadzu 9A instrument using OV-17 column. Light petroleum refers to the fraction b.p. 60–80° unless stated otherwise.

2-(5'-Methyl-2'-thenoyl)benzoic acid (9) : A mixture of purified phthalic anhydride (0.1 mol), anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.22 mol) and dry nitrobenzene (50 ml) was stirred at 55–60° for 1 h. To it was then added 2-methylthiophene (0.1 mol) slowly and dropwise at 40–45°. The mixture was stirred for 1 h, hydrolysed with ice-cold 6 *N* HCl and the usual work-up afforded 9 (89%), m.p. 130° (benzene); ν_{\max} 1630 and 1690; δ 2.55 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 6.75 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, ArH), 7.1 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, ArH), 7.45–7.6 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.1 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH).

2-(5'-Methyl-2'-thenyl)benzoic acid (10) : The keto acid (9; 0.0122 mol) was refluxed with 50% aqueous ammonia (163 ml), copper sulphate (0.08 g) and zinc dust (8.0 g). After usual work-up the reduced acid (10) was isolated whose homogeneity was checked by tlc, (74%), m.p. 118° (light petroleum); ν_{\max} 1685; δ 2.4 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 4.55 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 6.5 (1H, d, J 3.3 Hz, ArH), 6.6 (1H, d, J 3.3 Hz, ArH), 7.2–7.6 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.1 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH).

*2-Methyl-4-acetoxynaphtho[2,3-*b*]thiophene (11)* : A

solution of the reduced acid (**10**; 0.0095 mol) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.15 g) in acetic acid (15 ml) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was boiled for 1 h. After work-up, the resulting crude solid acetoxynaphthothiophene (**11**) was crystallised and its homogeneity was checked by tlc, (71%), m.p. 142° (light petroleum); ν_{\max} 1755; δ 2.48 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.64 (3H, s, COCH₃) and 7.36–8.64 (6H, m, ArH).

2-Methylnaphtho[2,3-b]thiophene (**6**) : A solution of the acetoxy compound (**11**; 0.002 mol) in 10% aqueous NaOH solution (20 ml) and toluene (2 ml) was boiled with zinc dust (3.0 g) under nitrogen for 24 h. After usual work-up, the product so obtained was purified by column chromatography, whose homogeneity was checked by tlc, (51.3%), m.p. 170°; δ 2.56 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 6.98 (1H, s, Ar-3H), 8.05 (1H, s, Ar-4H), 8.16 (1H, s, Ar-9H) and 7.31–7.87 (4H, m, Ar-5H, -6H, -7H, -8H).

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References

1. S. C. Sengupta and P. K. Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 653, 660, 815; P. K. Sen, S. Lahiri and T. K. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 821; P. K. Sen, S. Lahiri, P. Pal, G. Chatterjee and B. Maity, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1998, **37**, 768.
2. P. K. Sen and S. Lahiri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 741.
3. P. K. Sen and B. Kundu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 847; 1983, **60**, 303; P. K. Sen, S. Lahiri and B. Kundu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, **24**, 1280.
4. G. Jones and M. J. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1977, 505.